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Research Article

**IMPACT OF SUPPLEMENTATION OF ZINC ON THE
OUTCOME OF PREGNANCY IN FEMALES SUFFERING FROM
GESTATIONAL DIABETES****¹Dr Syeda Sehar Naqvi, ²Dr Gul Meena Manzoor, ²Dr Ammara Aslam**¹Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad²University Medical and Dental College, Faisalabad**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**ABSTRACT:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to interrogate the impacts of supplementation of the zinc on the outcome of pregnancy in the females from the gestation diabetes.

Methodology: We divided the 60 females suffering from the gestational diabetes in their 32nd week of gestation to receive the twenty-five-milligram zinc sulfate orally every day as research or placebo as control. Then, the comparison of the both groups carried out about the needs of the insulin doses, macrosomia & pre-eclampsia.

Results: The requirement of the insulin & alterations in dosage during investigation were very low in the group of patients in comparison with the group of healthy controls. Females in the group of zinc supplementation had very low percentage of the large neonates in comparison with the healthy controls. There were no important disparities between the members of both groups about the rate of occurrence of pre-eclampsia & cesarean sections.

Conclusions: This research work showed that the supplementation of the zinc in pregnancy females suffering from the diabetes during pregnancy period could decrease the requirements of insulin and improve the control of the blood glucose among these patients & it may decrease the incidence of macrosomia.

KEY WORDS: Gestation, Zinc, Supplementation, Pregnancy, Neonates, Diabetes, Preeclampsia.

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INTRODUCTION:

GDM (Gestational Diabetes Mellitus) is very common problem of health in the period of pregnancy. It is main reason of adverse maternal & fetal outcome and it increases risk factor for Type-2 diabetes. Diabetes can be the reason of the induction of the oxidative stress among mothers & fetus that can be the reason behind fatal fetal consequence as distress of fetal, macrosomia & some other congenital abnormalities [1]. There is evidence that in the complication of the Type-2 diabetes, the concentration of the levels of magnesium & zinc were highly reduced, possibly suggesting less antioxidant condition in that state [2]. The levels of the serum zinc condition in the patients of diabetes are very less as compared to the controls [3]. The dietary supplementation of the zinc decreased hyperglycemia [4] & performed vital parts in regulation of the metabolism of lipid and carbohydrates [2].

In GDM just like the Type-2 diabetes, in addition to the resistance to insulin, there is also the availability of the problem of secretion of insulin and because of significance of levels of zinc serum on the function of insulin, there is notable role of the deficiency of zinc in the pregnancy [2, 4]. There are various research works about the less levels of zinc serum in the patients of diabetes & positive impact of the supplementation of the zinc on the control of the blood glucose of Type-2 diabetic patients [2, 5] due to controversial findings [1, 3, 6] about the levels of zinc serum in diabetes during gestation period and the deficiency of the obvious research works about the impact of the supplementation of zinc on the fetal and maternal abnormalities due to GDM, this research work aimed to investigate the impacts of supplementation of the zinc on the pregnancy outcome on the pregnant females suffering from the GDM.

METHODOLOGY

This research work conducted in the Gynecological Department of Allied Hospital Faisalabad from June 2017 to March 2019. Most of the patients were in their 24-28 gestation weeks. Fifty gram OGTT test carried out for all the pregnant females, all the patients were available as positive for the screening tests. The

diagnosis of the gestational diabetes carried out by two values of the serum glucose which were greater than mentioned levels: one hundred and five mg/dl post fasting, one hundred and ninety mg/dl at one hour, one hundred and sixty-five mg/dl at two hours or one hundred and forty-five mg/dl at three hours [7]. The females suffering from other serious diseases which can affect the metabolism of the glucose were not the part of this research work. In the duration of screening, we diagnosed sixty females with gestational diabetes. The ethical committee of the hospital gave the approval to conduct this research work. We took written consent from every female before the start of the research work. In the group of zinc, females received twenty-five milligram zinc sulfate through oral way every day. Other group received five milligram placebo.

We continued the management of the both supplementation until the completion of gestation age. In both of the groups, the average gestation age was 39.0 ± 1 week. We check the fasting blood sugar and blood sugar for every patient and we maintained the level of glucose at level of less than one hundred and five for fasting & less than one hundred and twenty mg/dl for two hours after the glucose meal. At the final stage, we compared both groups about the need of the dosage of insulin, birth weight & pre-eclampsia. T test, Chi square test & Fisher exact method were in use for the analysis and comparison of various variables

RESULTS:

We were unable to find any important disparity among the participants of both groups in the initial stage of the research work about age, body mass index & levels of the serum zinc. Additionally, the alterations in body mass index of both groups were not important as mentioned in Table-1. All females of research and control groups found with diabetes & required therapy of insulin and their treatment carried out with insulin in this research work. There was no important disparity among the participants of both groups about the range of dose of insulin in the initial stage of the research work.

Table-I: Patients' Characteristics and Insulin Changes in the Case (Zn) and the Control (Placebo) Groups

Variables	Zn (n=30)		Control (n=30)		P.V
	Mean	St Dev	Mean	St Dev	
Age	28.300	3.130	28.600	3.230	0.7780
Body Mass Index	26.300	1.270	26.400	1.490	0.7740
Insulin Dosage(IU) (in beginning)	16.360	5.470	15.230	6.860	0.4820
Insulin Dosage(IU) (at the end)	25.130	10.780	32.760	11.910	0.0120
Insulin dosage changes(IU)	8.760	9.630	17.530	10.540	0.0010
Serum zinc levels (pg/dl)	61.430	5.090	63.200	5.470	0.2000

In the last stage of the research work, the analysis displayed that requirement of the insulin & alterations in dosage during examination was much lower in the group of Zn in comparison with the healthy controls. The average neonatal weight & standard deviation at the time of birth in the zinc & control groups were 3729 ± 300 and 3867 ± 313 correspondingly. Females in the group of Zn

found with low percentage of large neonates in comparison with the healthy controls (6.70% verses 33.30%). This disparity was much important. We found no statistical disparities between the supplementation of the zinc & healthy controls about the rates of prevalence of pre-eclampsia & delivery through cesarean section (Table-2).

Table-II: Frequency of Delivery Method, Preeclampsia and Macrosomia Regarding to Zn Supplementation in Diabetic Mothers

Variables		Zn		Control		p value	Odds Ratio	Conf. Interval
		No	Percent	No	Percent			
Delivery Method	NVD	14.0	46.70	8.0	26.70	0.1080	2.4060	0.8160 7.0950
	C/S	16.0	53.30	22.0	73.30			
Preeclampsia	Yes	4.0	13.30	5.0	16.70	1.0000	1.3000	0.3130 5.4040
	No	26.0	86.70	25.0	83.30			
Macrosomia	Yes	2.0	6.70	10.0	33.30	0.0100	7.0000	1.3810 35.4780
	No	28.0	93.30	20.0	66.70			

Note: NVD, Normal Vaginal Delivery-C/S, Cesarean Section

DISCUSSION:

This research work displayed that the supplementation of zinc in the patients of GDM can decrease the requirement of insulin & improve the control of blood glucose and it has the ability to decrease the rate of prevalence of macrosomia. There are many research works about the deficiency of Zn and labor abnormalities. Tamura also worked on the outcome of pregnancy among females receiving supplementation of Zn. He displayed the supplementation of Zn in females with no diabetes can be the reason of high birth weight & circumference of head of newborns at the time of birth [8], the findings of this research work are not in favor with the outcome of current research work.

Various findings may be because of different traits of patients. Bo displayed that levels of Zn serum in the females with pregnancy (twenty-four to twenty-eight gestation age) were available with lower GTT in comparison with the group of controls and he concluded that the levels of zinc in serum were available with association with gestation hyperglycemia [1]. Wang in his research work displayed that the content of the zinc in the females with pregnancy suffering from GDM was very less in comparison with the females with normal pregnancy [3]. Al-Saleh stated from his research work that there was not any important disparity between obese females with diabetes & obese females with no diabetes about the level of zinc serum [6]. These results were also opposite from the research works of Bo & Wang as well as current research work. These differences in the outcomes of different research works were because of the different ways methodological ways. The

utilization of Zn for the prevention of the pre-eclampsia was not the subject of research works but some research works have concluded very less or no advantage [9].

Ilhan concluded an association between the decrease in the level of serum Zn & pre-eclampsia [10]. This current research work did not display any important disparity between the patients having supplementation of Zn & placebo groups about the birth weight & rate of incidence of pre-eclampsia. The recent research work did not display any important disparity about the rate of deliveries through cesarean section among patients chose for the cesarean surgery because of macrosomia in both groups of the research works possibly due to the misestimating the weight of fetal before child birth.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work concluded that supplementation of the zinc among females suffering from GDM can decrease the needs of insulin and improve the control of blood glucose of these patients & it may decrease the rate of incidence of the macrosomia.

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